

西安财经大学 信息学院

编译原理 实验报告

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实验名称：预测分析 LL(1)

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一、实验目的

1. 掌握 FIRST 和 FOLLOW 集合的构造方法；
2. 掌握预测分析表的构造；
3. 了解自顶向下预测分析的过程。

二、实验内容

1. 设计并实现 FIRST 和 FOLLOW 集合的求解算法；
2. 构造预测分析表并输出；
3. 判断该文法是否为 LL(1)文法；

三、实验要求

1. 输入一个文法并输出显示；
2. 分别编写求 FIRST 和 FOLLOW 集合的函数；
3. 构造预测分析表并输出；
4. 根据预测分析表判断是否为 LL(1)文法；
5. 对任意输入串进行预测分析并给出分析过程。（选做）

四、数据结构和算法设计

1. 文法的存储

接下来我们约定: 文法的输入需要遵守 $\text{L}^{\text{A}}\text{T}_{\text{E}}\text{X}$ 语法并保证符号之间用空格隔开, ϵ 表示空串, 一组非终结符需要加粗。对于用户来说, 这样的输入输出较为美观, 对于程序来说, 可以直接根据空格拆分文法的每一个符号。

根据输入约定, 构造数据结构 *rules*, 可以通过 Python 字典实现, 对于每一个字典项, 用列表存储文法的条目, 每个条目是一个列表, 作为符号序列, 即 $\text{Dict}[\text{str}, \text{List}[\text{List}[\text{str}]]]$, 该字典的键 (key) 为非终结符集合, 同时记录非终结符集合 *terminals*, 便于接下来算法处理, 也要记录开始符号, 便于接下来使用

例如, 对于

$$\begin{aligned} E &\rightarrow TE' \\ E' &\rightarrow +TE \mid \epsilon \\ T &\rightarrow FT' \\ T' &\rightarrow *FT' \mid \epsilon \\ F &\rightarrow (E) \mid \mathbf{id} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

按照输入约定, 输入一个列表 *g* 表示文法 (1)

```
g = [r"E \to T E'",
     r"E' \to + T E' | \epsilon ",
     r"T \to F T'",
     r"T' \to * F T' | \epsilon ",
     r"F \to ( E ) | \textbf{id}"]
```

在 python 中存储结构如下

```
defaultdict(list,
             {'E': [['T', "E"]],
              "E'": [['+', 'T', "E"], ['\epsilon']],
              'T': [['F', "T"]],
              "T'": [['*', 'F', "T"], ['\epsilon']],
              'F': [['(', 'E', ')'], ['\textbf{id}']]})
```

更多详细的说明可以查阅本项目的 API 说明文档 https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ll1_parser/api/

2. first 集合的构造

程序 $\text{first}(X)$ 集合规则如下

1. 如果 X 为终结符, 则 $\text{first}(X) = \{X\}$

2. 若 X 为非终结符, $X \rightarrow Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_k (k \geq 1), Y_1 Y_2 \dots Y_{i-1} \xrightarrow{*} \epsilon$, 即 $\epsilon \in \text{first}(Y_j), j = 1, 2, \dots, i-1$, 将 $\text{first}(X_i)$ 中所有元素加入 $\text{first}(X)$
3. 对于 $X \rightarrow \epsilon$, 直接将 ϵ 加入 $\text{first}(X)$

根据对应规则和数据结构设计 算法 1

算法 1 生成终结符的 first 集合并存储

create_first()

```

1  queue nonterminals_rules          ▷ 存储暂时没法处理的终结符
2  for left, rule in rules:          ▷ 迭代每一条规则
3      x ← rule[0]                    ▷ x 为产生式左边第一个符号
4      if x ∈ terminals:              ▷ 产生式的第一个符号是终结符
5          first(left) ← first(left) ∪ {x}    ▷ 将终结符加入左部的 first 集合
6      else if x = ε:
7          contain_empty ← contain_empty ∪ {x}
8      else:                            ▷ 终结符稍后处理
9          nonterminals_rules.enqueue((left, rule))    ▷ 将对应的信息入队
10 while nonterminals_rules:          ▷ 若队不空
11     left, rule ← nonterminals.dequeue()
12     x ← rule[0]
13     if x ∈ firsts:                  ▷ firsts 为当前有 first 集合的非终结符的集合,
                                        ▷ 也就是说, 他们已经有非终结符在 first 集合中
14         first(left) ← first(left) ∪ first(x)
15     else:
16         nonterminals_rules.enqueue((left, rule))
17     if x ∈ contain_empty:           ▷ x 可能包含空串
18         if rule[1]:                  ▷ 有其他的符号
19             nonterminals.enqueue((left, rule[1 :]))    ▷ 将后续字符加入处理队列

```

算法 1 的对应 python 实现见 https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/_modules/LL1Parser/#LL1Parser.create_first

类似的, 可以求表达式的文法, 我们可以利用 算法 1 的结果。

算法 2 求 $first(\alpha)$

get_first(α)

- 1 $x \leftarrow \alpha[0]$ $\triangleright x$ 为表达式第一个字符
 - 2 **if** $x \in terminals$ **or** $x = \epsilon$:
 - 3 **return** $\{x\}$
 - 4 $s \leftarrow first(x)$
 - 5 **while** $\epsilon \in s$:
 - 6 $n \leftarrow get_first(\alpha[1:])$ \triangleright 递归的求出接下来的表达式的 first 集合
 - 7 $s \leftarrow s \cup n$
 - 8 **return** s
-

这部分代码在https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/_modules/LL1Parser/#LL1Parser.get_first中实现

3. follow 集合的构造

follow 集合规则如下

1. 如果 S 为终结符, 则输入串的结束标记符 $\$ \in follow(S)$
2. 对于产生式 $A \rightarrow \alpha B \beta$, $(first(\beta) - \{\epsilon\}) \subset follow(B)$
3. 对于产生式 $A \rightarrow \alpha B$, 或 $A \rightarrow \alpha B \beta$, $\beta \xRightarrow{*} \epsilon$, 则 $follow(A) \subset follow(B)$

根据对应规则和数据结构设计 算法 3

算法 3 生成终结符的 first 集合并存储

```
create_follow()
1 follow( $S$ )  $\leftarrow$  follow( $s$ )  $\cup$   $\{\$$      $\triangleright$  将输入右标记加入起始符的 follow 集合中
2 queue  $q$      $\triangleright$  保存  $(A, B)$  follow( $B$ )  $\subset$  follow( $A$ )
3 for  $l, \alpha$  in rules:
4      $add(\alpha, \epsilon)$      $\triangleright$  在规则最后添加空串标记
5     for  $i = 0$  to length( $\alpha$ ):
6         if  $\alpha[i] \in nonterminals$ :
7             if  $\alpha[i + 1] \in nonterminals$ :
8                 follow( $\alpha[i]$ )  $\leftarrow$  follow( $\alpha[i]$ ) + first( $\alpha[i + 1]$ ) -  $\{\epsilon\}$ 
9                 if  $\alpha[i + 1] \in \{X | X \xrightarrow{*} \epsilon\}$ :
10                     $q.enqueue((\alpha[i], l))$ 
11                else if  $\alpha[i + 1] \in terminals$ :
12                    follow( $\alpha[i]$ ) = follow( $\alpha[i]$ )  $\cup$   $\{\alpha[i + 1]\}$ 
13             $q.enqueue((None, None))$      $\triangleright$  结尾的标志符
14            has_enlarged = False
15        while  $q$ :
16             $t, \ell = q.dequeue()$ 
17            if  $\ell$  is None:
18                if not has_enlarged:
19                    break     $\triangleright$  集合不在增大，退出
20                else :
21                    has_enlarged  $\leftarrow$  False
22            else :
23                 $A \leftarrow follow(t)$      $\triangleright$  末尾作为较大的集合
24                 $B \leftarrow follow(\ell)$      $\triangleright B \subset A$ 
25                 $N \leftarrow A \cup B$ 
26                if  $A \neq N$ :     $\triangleright$  集合已经被扩大
27                    has_enlarged  $\leftarrow$  True
28                    follow( $t$ )  $\leftarrow N$ 
29                 $q.enqueue((t, \ell))$ 
```

算法 3 的对应 python 实现见 https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/_modules/LL1Parser/#LL1Parser.create_follow

4. 语法分析表的构造

语法分析表需要读写 $M[A, a]$ 的结构，可以用两重字典嵌套，对应值为一条产生式 $List[str]$ ，最终数据类型为 $Dict[str, Dict[str, List[str]]]$

语法分析表规则如下，对于产生式 $A \rightarrow \alpha$ ，执行

1. $\forall a \in \text{first}(\alpha)$ ，将 $A \rightarrow \alpha$ 加入 $M[A, a]$
2. 若 $\epsilon \in \text{first}(\alpha)$ ，对 \forall 终结符 $b \in \text{follow}(A)$ ，将 $A \rightarrow \alpha$ 加入 $M[A, b]$ 。若 $\epsilon \in \text{first}(\alpha)$ 且 $\$ \in \text{follow}(A)$ ，将 $A \rightarrow \alpha$ 加入 $M[A, \$]$ 。
3. 若加入语法分析表时有别的产生式，抛出异常

根据对应规则和数据结构设计算法 4

算法 4 构造语法分析表

```
create_table()
```

```
1 for A,  $\alpha$  in rules:
2      $f \leftarrow \text{get\_first}(\alpha)$     ▷ 获得产生式的 first 集合
3     for a in f:
4         add( $M[A, a], \alpha$ )    ▷ 具体实现函数中会检测  $M[A, a]$  中是否已经有产生式并抛出异常
5     if  $\epsilon \in f$ :
6         for  $b \in \text{follow}(A)$ :
7             add( $M[A, b], \alpha$ )
8         if  $\$ \in \text{follow}(A)$ :
9             add( $M[A, \$], \alpha$ )
```

算法 4 的对应 python 实现见 https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/_modules/LL1Parser/#LL1Parser.create_table

五、实验步骤与结果

1. 测试文法的输入

根据上述数据结构首先测试文法的输入与保存，对于文法1
在 python 中导入写好的库，调用

```
from LL1Parser import LL1Parser
g = [r"E \to T E'",
     r"E' \to + T E | \epsilon ",
     r"T \to F T'",
```


表 1 文法 (1) 语意分析表

terminal	id	\$	*	(+)
E	$E \rightarrow TE'$			$E \rightarrow TE'$		
E'		$E' \rightarrow \epsilon$			$E' \rightarrow +TE'$	$E' \rightarrow \epsilon$
T	$T \rightarrow FT'$			$T \rightarrow FT'$		
T'		$T' \rightarrow \epsilon$	$T' \rightarrow *FT'$		$T' \rightarrow \epsilon$	$T' \rightarrow \epsilon$
F	$F \rightarrow \mathbf{id}$			$F \rightarrow (E)$		

4. 测设非 LL(1) 文法

下面测试非 LL(1) 文法4

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &\rightarrow iEtSS' \\
 &\quad | a \\
 S' &\rightarrow eS \\
 &\quad | \epsilon \\
 E &\rightarrow b
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

非 LL(1) 文法在将语法添加到语法分析表的时候会报错，此时抛出异常如下

```

RuntimeError: It isn't a LL(1) grammar,
    new added M[S'][e] = ['\epsilon']
    conflict with existing M[S'][e] = ['e', 'S']
    parsing table
    
```

六、实验总结

这次报告网上现有的资料较少，搜出的代码可读性不高，所以本文算法设计根据编译原理^[1]的描述直接做出，可能算法不够精炼，但是实现的过程感受到该书描述的严谨细致，通过语言描述可以直接构造相应的算法和数据结构。

代码实现是通过我对规则的理解给出，实现的过程中也在不断改进美化代码和简化逻辑，这样的过程增加了我程序设计的经验和技巧，利于接下来进一步学习。另外代码的许多部分不够简洁，如 $\text{first}(X)$ 和 $\text{first}(\alpha)$ 的算法有逻辑重叠，希望在有时间的时候对代码进行优化。

通过这些设计研究，我了解了计算机设计的抽象问题，分析问题，解决问题的方法和步骤，这些思考和实现有利于接下来的程序设计和逻辑思维。

参考文献

- [1] Alfred V Aho, Ravi Sethi, and Jeffrey D Ullman. *Compilers, principles, techniques*, volume 7. Addison Wesley, 2 edition, 2006.

附录 A 依赖的安装

本文代码的依赖如下

```
network2tikz
IPython
jupyter-sphinx
```

可以通过以下命令在清华镜像网站安装全部

```
pip install -i http://mirrors.aliyun.com/pypi/simple \
--trusted-host mirrors.aliyun.com/pypi/simple/ \
-r requirements.txt
```

附录 B 参考文档

- API文档:https://compilers-homework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ll1_parser/api/
- 完整项目 https://github.com/chenboshuo/compilers_homework

附录 C 源代码

```
from collections import defaultdict, deque
from typing import *
from IPython.display import display, Math, Latex
import itertools

class LL1Parser:
    r"""a set of algorithms to analyse the LL(1) grammer

    :param rules: the LL(1) grammer, you need input using latex grammer and
        sparated by spaces.

    for instance, in you want to input:

    :math:`E \to T E`
```

```
:math:`E` \to + T E | \epsilon`
```

```
:math:`T` \to F T`
```

```
:math:`T` \to *F T' | \epsilon`
```

```
:math:`F` \to ( E ) | \textbf{id}`
```

then run:

```
.. jupyter-execute::
```

```
from LL1Parser import LL1Parser
g = [r"E \to T E",
     r"E' \to + T E' | \epsilon ",
     r"T \to F T'",
     r"T' \to * F T' | \epsilon ",
     r"F \to ( E ) | \textbf{id}"]
grammer = LL1Parser(g)
```

```
:type rules: List[str]
```

```
:param start_symbol: the start symbol
```

```
:type start_symbol: str, optional
```

then you can display the rules using `display_rules()`, for example:

```
.. jupyter-execute::
```

```
grammer.display_rules()
```

You can see the first sets and follow sets using `display_first_sets()`, for examples:

```
.. jupyter-execute::
```

```
grammer.display_first_sets()
```

Similarly, you can see the follow set using:

```
.. jupyter-execute::
```

```
grammer.display_follow_sets()
```

The `LL1Parser.display_parsing_table` can show the parsing table

```

.. jupyter-execute::

    grammar.display_parsing_table()

"""

def __init__(self, rules: List[str], start_symbol: str = None) -> None:
    """init the LL(1) grammar
    """
    # set the start symbol
    if start_symbol:
        self.start_symbol = start_symbol # : the start symbol
    else:
        self.start_symbol = rules[0].split()[0]
    # save rules
    self.rules: Dict[str, List[str]] = defaultdict(list)
    """the rules of the grammar,
    `self.rules[T] = L`,
    `L[i]= items`,
    `items[k] = symbol`,
    where `T` is a terminal,
    `i` is the index of alternatives
    `items` is the list of the symbols of a rule
    """

    self.terminals: set = set()
    """
    The list of terminals in table parsing table
    (include $, not include :math:`\epsilon`)
    """

    for rule in rules:
        alternatives = rule.split('|') # find rules connect by |
        first_part = alternatives[0].split()
        left = first_part[0] # the nonterminal can find in the first part
        # add elements except left symbol and ->
        self.rules[left].append(first_part[2:])
        self.terminals.update(first_part[2:])

        for alternative in alternatives[1:]:
            alternative_symbols = alternative.split()
            self.rules[left].append(alternative_symbols)
            self.terminals.update(alternative_symbols)

    self.terminals = self.terminals - \
        set(self.rules.keys()) - set([r'\epsilon'])
    self.terminals.update([r'\$'])

```

```

# create first
self.first: Dict[str, set] = defaultdict(set)
"""the first symbol dicts
"""
self.contains_empty: set = set([r'\epsilon'])
"""the set of terminals that contains empty strings
"""
self.create_first()

# create follow set
self.follow = defaultdict(set)
"""the follow set of every nonterminal
"""
self.create_follow()

self.parsing_table: Dict[str, Dict[str, List[str]]] \
    = defaultdict(dict)
""" the parsing table
self.parsing_table[A][a] = (rule)
where A is the nonterminal at the left of rule,
a is the nonterminal
"""

# create parsing table
self.create_table()

def display_rules(self, raw=False):
    """display the latex code of the gammer

:param raw: show the raw code, defaults to False
:type raw: bool, optional
"""
    begin = r"\begin{array}{ll}" + "\n"
    end = r"\end{array}"+ "\n"

    for left, rules in self.rules.items():
        s = self.display_rule(left, rules[0])
        for r in rules[1:]:
            s += self.display_rule(left, rule=r, is_alternative=True)
        begin += s

    if raw:
        print(begin+end)

display(Math(begin+end))

```

```

def display_rule(self, left: str,
                 rule: List[str], new_line=True,
                 array_environment=True,
                 is_alternative=False) -> str:
    """display a rule

    :param left: left symbol
    :type left: str
    :param rule: the list of the rule
    :type rule: List[str]
    :param new_line: whether need a new line at the end, defaults to True
    :type new_line: bool, optional
    :param array_environment: whether the expression in array environment
    :type array_environment: bool
    :param is_alternative: whether the rule is the alternative, defaults to False
    :type is_alternative: bool, optional
    :return: the latex string of the rule
    :rtype: str
    """
    if not is_alternative: # need left symbol
        s = "\t"+left
        if array_environment:
            s += r" & " # TODO handle the & symbol
            s += r" \to "
        else:
            s = "\t\t"
            if array_environment:
                s += r"&"
                s += r"\;, \, |;\,|"

    s += " ".join(rule)
    if new_line:
        s += r" \\" + "\n"

    return s

def create_first(self):
    """create the first sets

    :ivar nonterminals: the queue to save the first nonterminal of
        a rule
    :vartype nonterminals: collections.deque
    :ivar can_emptystring: the set of nonterminals can be empty
    :vartype can_emptystring: set
    """
    nonterminals = deque()

```

```

for left, rule in self.iter_rules():
    if rule[0] in self.terminals: # symbol rule[0] is terminal
        self.first[left].add(rule[0])
    elif rule[0] == r'\epsilon':
        self.contains_empty.add(left)
    else: # rule[0] is nonterminal
        nonterminals.append((left, rule))

while nonterminals:
    left, rule = nonterminals.popleft()
    if rule[0] in self.first: # first symbol is nonterminal
        self.first[left].update(self.first[rule[0]])
    else: # pending
        nonterminals.append((left, rule))

    if rule[0] in self.contains_empty: # first symbol can empty string
        if rule[1:]:
            nonterminals.append((left, rule[1:]))

def iter_rules(self) -> tuple:
    """iter all the rules

    :yield: the iterator of (left,rule)
    :rtype: Iterator[tuple]
    """

    for left, rules in self.rules.items():
        for rule in rules:
            yield (left, rule)

def display_sets(self, name, raw=False):
    """display the sets

    :param names: the set names(first, follow)
    :type name: str
    :param raw: show the raw latex code, defaults to False
    :type raw: bool, optional
    """
    begin = r"\begin{array}{ll}" + "\n"
    end = r"\end{array}" + "\n"
    contents = begin
    for left, first_set in self.__dict__[name].items():
        s = "\t" + r"\mathrm{" + name + r"}(" + left + r") &= \{"
        s += ", ".join(list(first_set))
        s += r"\} \\" + "\n"
        contents += s
    contents += end

```

```

if raw:
    print(contents)

display(Math(contents))

def display_first_sets(self, raw=False):
    """render the first(i) in jupyter notebook

    :param raw: the raw code of latex, defaults to False
    :type raw: bool, optional
    """
    self.display_sets(raw=raw, name='first')

def display_follow_sets(self, raw=False):
    """render the follow(i) in jupyter notebook

    :param raw: the raw code of LaTeX, defaults to False
    :type raw: bool, optional
    """
    self.display_sets(raw=raw, name='follow')

def create_follow(self):
    r"""create the follow sets of all nonterminals

    1. place the $ symbol in follow(S),
    where S is the start symbol,
    and $ is the input right endmarker

    2. if there is a production :math:`A \to \alpha B \beta`,
    then everything in `first(B)` except :math:`\epsilon`
    is in `follow(B)`

    3. if there is a production :math:`A \to \alpha B`,
    or a production :math:`A \to aB\beta`,
    where first(:math:`\beta`) contains :math:`\epsilon`,
    then everything in `follow(A)` is in `follow(B)`
    """

    self.follow[self.start_symbol].add(r'\$') # add end symbol
    to_union = deque() # (A,B) such that set B is the subset of set A
    empty_symbol = set([r'\epsilon'])
    for left, rule in self.iter_rules():
        for cur, post in \
            itertools.zip_longest(rule, rule[1:],
                                  fillvalue=r'\epsilon'):
            if cur in self.rules: # cur is nonterminal
                if post in self.rules: # post is nonterminal

```

```

        self.follow[cur].update(self.first[post]-empty_symbol)
    if post in self.contains_empty:
        # follow(cur) contains follow(left)
        to_union.append((cur, left))
    elif post in self.terminals:
        self.follow[cur].add(post)
to_union.append((None, None)) # add the terminal symbol
has_enlarged = False
while to_union:
    tail, left = to_union.popleft()
    if left is None:
        if not has_enlarged:
            break
        else:
            has_enlarged = False
            to_union.append((None, None))
    else:
        set_, subset = self.follow[tail], self.follow[left]
        new_set = set_.union(subset)
        if set_ != new_set:
            has_enlarged = True
            self.follow[tail] = new_set
            to_union.append((tail, left))

def add_to_table(self, left: str, terminal: str,
                rule: List[str]):
    r"""add the rule to the predictive parsing table

    :param left: the left of the production
    :type left: str
    :param terminal: the related terminal
    :type terminal: str
    :param rule: the rule of the right
    :type rule: List[str]
    :raises RuntimeError: conflict in add items,
        that means the grammer isn't LL(1) grammer.
        for example, if you have the grammer

    .. jupyter-execute::

        from IPython.display import display, Math, Latex
        w = [r"S \to i E t S S' | a",
             r"S' \to e S | \epsilon",
             r"E \to b"]
        for g in w:
            display(Math(g))

```

```

then you create the instance,
you will see the information

.. jupyter-execute::
   :raises:

       wrong = LL1Parser(w)
"""

if terminal in self.parsing_table[left] and rule != self.parsing_table[left][terminal]:
    raise RuntimeError(f""It isn't a LL(1) grammar,
new added M[{left}][{terminal}] = {rule}
conflict with existing M[{left}][{terminal}] = {self.parsing_table[left][terminal]}
parsing table.
""")
self.parsing_table[left][terminal] = rule

def create_table(self):
    r"""create a predictive parsing table
    For each production  $A \to \alpha$  of the grammar,
    do the following:

    1. For each terminal  $a$ , add  $A \to \alpha$ 
    to  $M[A,a]$ .

    2. If  $\epsilon$  in  $\text{first}(\alpha)$ ,
    then for each terminal  $b$  in  $\text{follow}(A)$ ,
    add  $A \to \alpha$  to  $M[A,b]$ .
    If  $\epsilon$  in  $\text{first}(\alpha)$ 
    and  $\$$  in  $\text{follow}(A)$ ,
    add  $A \to \alpha$  to  $M[A,\$]$  as well.
    """
    for left, rule in self.iter_rules():
        first = self.get_first(rule)
        for terminal in first:
            self.add_to_table(left=left, terminal=terminal, rule=rule)
        if r'\epsilon' in first: # epsilon is in first symbol
            for i in self.follow[left]: # every symbol should add to table
                self.add_to_table(left=left,
                                terminal=i, rule=rule)
        if r'\$' in self.follow[left]:
            self.add_to_table(left=left,
                            terminal=r'\$', rule=rule)

    # TODO calculate the first of production, and store them
    # Then calculate the first of nonterminal
def get_first(self, rule: List[str]) -> set:

```

```

r"""return the first symbol of a expression(calculate first(:math:\`alpha\`))

:param rule: the list of rule symbols
:type rule: List[str]
:return: the set of the first set
:rtype: set
"""
if rule[0] in self.terminals or rule[0] == r'\epsilon':
    return set([rule[0]])
first_set = self.first[rule[0]]
first_part = self.first[rule[0]]
while r'\epsilon' in first_part:
    first_part = self.get_first(rule[1:])
    first_set.update(first_part)

return first_set

def display_parsing_table(self, raw=False):
    begin = r"\begin{array}{|}"
    begin += r"|".join(["c"]*(len(self.terminals)+1))
    begin += r"}" + '\n'
    end = r"\end{array}"

    # create the header
    header = "\t\hline \n" + "\t" + r"\text{terminal}"
    for terminal in self.terminals:
        header += "\t&"
        header += terminal
    header += r"\ \hline" + "\n"
    cells = ""
    for nonterminal in self.rules.keys():
        line = "\t" + nonterminal
        for terminal in self.terminals:
            line += " \t&"
            if terminal in self.parsing_table[nonterminal]:
                line += self.display_rule(left=nonterminal,
                                          rule=self.parsing_table[nonterminal][terminal],
                                          new_line=False,
                                          array_environment=False)

            # line += r"\ \hline" + '\n'
        line += r"\ \ " + '\n'
        cells += line

    cells += r"\hline" + "\n"
    content = begin+header + cells + end
    display(Math(content))
if raw:

```

```
print(content)
```